

Water Problems and Challenges: A Case Study of Delhi NCR

Amrita Bajaj , Shahid Jamal, Aakash Upadhyay, Krishna Kumar and Manjeet Singh

Received: 27 December 2018

Reviewed and Accepted: 05 February 2019

Published: 10 March 2019

Introduction

Water is the basis of all living organisms that distinguishes our earth from other planets. It exists everywhere from polar ice caps to soils and cells of human beings. It contains both quality and quantity characteristics wherein quality refers to the availability of water while quantity describes physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of water. Water is considered a very powerful infrastructure-driven life support system in cities, but such finite sources became scarce in the current scenario. Inadequate water availability in cities has raised several problems including confrontation among people. On one side of cities, excess water in form of floods are killing millions while on another side due to degraded water supply, drought condition is prevailing. Delhi NCR is one such city, which is facing an acute shortage of water throughout the years and water quality has reached its lowest level due to unsafe and unhealthy practices. The quality and quantity of water widely depend on different components of the hydrological cycle including groundwater recharge, precipitation, evaporation, and surface water runoff. Human activities have a tremendous impact on water quality because they dumped hazardous waste into the environment by consuming several

Amrita Bajaj* (✉) ● Shahid Jamal ● Aakash Upadhyay*** ● Krishna Kumar+ ● Manjeet Singh++**

*Department of Geography, Shaheed Bhagat Singh College (M), University of Delhi, Delhi

**Department of Geography, Delhi School of Economics, University of Delhi, Delhi

***Department of Geography, Shyama Prasad Mukherjee College, University of Delhi, Delhi

+Department of Geography, Shaheed Bhagat Singh College (E), University of Delhi, Delhi

++Department of Geography, Miranda House, University of Delhi, Delhi

resources. It includes food, building materials, hydrocarbon fuels, and electronic gadgets. Further, the population explosion is deteriorating water quality in Delhi NCR and creating challenges for the industry, agriculture, and wildlife habitat.

Water quality is another important issue as poor water quality is one of the major reasons for various water diseases like typhoid, shigella, cholera, diarrhoea, and amoebiasis. The major factors for the decline in the city's water quality are industrial influents, regular leakage from septic tanks, sewage overflows and urban storm runoff, industrial waste disposal, and leakage from automobiles. Anything that human beings are injecting into the environment eventually either organic or inorganic substances are mixed with water bodies. Hence, the decline in water quality is a potential threat degrading the health of the city. A little decline in water quality will prove a disaster for major economic sectors of the city. Thereby, people's working efficiency will reduce and the money which is kept for development programs will be diverted to the public health sector. The exponential growth in the city's urbanization over a few decades is posing threat to the availability of water and its quality. Safe drinking water and sanitation is quite a significant parameter for urban development and the government is addressing such challenges in the program. Delhi NCR already covered under smart cities mission in 2015 wherein special emphasis is given regarding sanitation and water safe drinking water availability to all. Earlier, World Health Organisation (WHO) and United Nations (UN) highlighted the significance of uninterrupted water supply and sanitation for the comprehensive growth of cities. UN had declared the year 2003 as the *International Year of Freshwater* to create awareness among the global community for sustainable and judicious use of water.

Research Objectives

The study investigates existing water quantity and quality challenges in Delhi NCR with suggestive measures to overcome the challenges.

Study Area

Delhi besides being the national capital is renowned as a historical and ancient city of India. It is situated in the northern part of India and is spread over 1483 sq. km. Delhi is situated at the bank of the Yamuna River between

the 28° 12" N to 28° 53" N latitude and 76° 50" to E 77° 23" E longitude. In the city, around 90% of the land area has availability of potable water up to 60 meters. It receives 715mm of an annual average rainfall, of which 75% rainfall receives during the month of July, August, and September. It is one of the largest cities in terms of geographical area and counted the highest population density 36155 per/sq.km across India. It has around 6343 slums spread over a large area of the city with approximately one million households. It has 9 villages and two tehsils which are fully urban in nature.

Fig. 1 Location of Study area

Database and Research Methodology

Database and research methodology are described as the distinguishing backbone of any research. Both primary and secondary data sources were applied for analysis in the study while qualitative and quantitative techniques together with empirical method were used to get the desired result. A household survey based on purposive participatory sampling was conducted in a different region of Delhi including Kanniappa Colony and Rajeswari Nagar recently. Regarding secondary data, the National Institute of Urban Affairs, Government of National Capital Territory of Delhi, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Planning Commission, District Census Hand book-Delhi have used a detailed analysis of the study. Apart from these, several journals, books, newspapers, magazines, and government websites were referred. The collected data are represented in tables, bar diagrams, pie diagrams, and trend lines.

Results and Discussion

a. Water Supply and Demand in Delhi

Delhi Jal Board is engaged in providing piped potable water to the individual household in Delhi. It supplies filtered and pure water and is committed to the augmentation of the supply and has taken several steps in this direction. The Board provides the average availability of 50 gallons per capita per day of filtered water to the New Delhi Municipal Corporation (NDMC). NDMC supplies water through a huge network of pumping stations, reservoirs, tanks. The task is highly challenging due to the swiftly growing city and continuous increasing population from neighbouring states like Haryana, Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Uttarakhand (Fig. 2). Although, the city has good networking of many treatment plants and booster pumping stations to clean water and meet the city's water demand.

Fig. 2 Population Growth of Delhi from 1901 to 2011 (Compiled from District Census Handbook-Delhi, 2011 and Prepared by Author)

b. Quantity, Quality, and Sources of Water

Mother earth is blessed with an enormous quantity of water, but the uneven distribution of water has resulted in its unsuitable usage. Water is supplied to around 18 million people in the National capital through many water supply networks. It is composed of 105 underground reservoirs and 11,350 km of pipeline for rationalized and smooth distribution of water supply. There are around four sources of raw supply in Delhi that include Yamuna River, Bhakra storage, Ganga River, and groundwater (Fig. 3). Yamuna River accounts for the highest (40%) proportion of raw water supply followed by Bhakra storage (26%), Ganga River (25%), and groundwater accounts for the lowest (9%). Delhi uses an average of 835 million gallons per day (MGD) of raw water from various sources. The Ganga River has the highest water capacity in Delhi followed by Bhakra storage, Yamuna River and the lowest is groundwater (Fig. 4). The water supply capacity and treatment capacity was 650 MGD in the year 2002, has increased to 1016 MGD in 2016.

Source: District Census Handbook, 2011 and Prepared by Author

Fig. 3 Sources of Raw Water Supply to Delhi

Source: District Census Handbook, 2011 and Prepared by Author

Fig. 4 Water Capacity in Delhi

c. Water Supply Distribution System

The existing water supply Distribution System in Delhi is inadequate as there is more demand for water, but the supply is inadequate to meet the demand. In summers, the gap between demand and supply of water has widened in the city. Although there was a regular supply of water 24X7, such water supply was limited to a few hours during day and night time. Now, it has been restricted to only two hours in the morning and two hours in the evening. During, designated hours, if dwellers are failed to store water, they

have to wait for the next day or buy water from outside sources like tanks. There are around 300 boosting stations and 155 overhead tanking with a total capacity of 192.49 million litres per day (MLD) in Delhi. The major challenge for poor water supply in the city is the presence of outdated and obsolete distribution channels. These were around 50 years old and no further up-gradation was made so far. There are several incidences of water pipe leakages due to urban sprawl, encroachment, illegal colonies, and development of slums along with sensitive supply areas (Table 1). Many times, sewage lines join main water supply lines and caused a huge interruption in the water supply to the affected area.

Table 1 Sources of Drinking Water Supply in Delhi

S.N.	Source of Drinking Water	Total Households (%)	Slum Households (%)
1.	Piped water supply	81.3	84.3
	I. From treated source	75.2	73.3
	II. From untreated source	6.1	11.0
2.	Covered well	0.1	0.1
3.	Hand pump	5.3	5.4
4.	Tube well	8.4	6.1
5.	Tank, pond, lake	1.2	1.4
6.	Other sources	3.7	2.7
	Availability		
1.	Within the premises	78.4	50.9
2.	Near the premises	15.4	39.6
3.	Away	6.2	9.5

Source District Census Handbook, 2011 (Prepared by Author)

d. Pricing policy

Delhi is one of the prominent business hubs of India and its population is increasing rapidly over the past few decades (Fig. 1). The problem of drinking water is usually a concern and creates havoc in the city because more people are dependent on the existing available water sources. Thereby, several questions have been raised regarding water quality, and several surveys were conducted either by researchers or by any eminent organizations. After the analysis of such survey, it was concluded that majority of regions in the city have contaminated water sources. It includes several chemicals like pesticides, mercury, and arsenic causing several unwanted diseases like Hepatitis A and gastroenteritis. Around 80% of diseases are related to water contamination in the city.

Regarding this, a pricing policy is a better option to avoid unnecessary waste of water for several unproductive purposes like vehicle cleaning. The pricing policy includes billing in the current situation and those who have Delhi Jal Board connection have to make regular water. Although, there is a waive-off for the first 20,000 liters of water bill payment according to new Delhi government guidelines. Public-Private partnership is another step to improve water quality in the city. Protection of drinking water is a shared and common responsibility of all including individuals, water suppliers, local government, civil societies, Non-Government Organisations (NGOs) businessmen, and industrialists. The concrete partnership in the arena of retail distribution, source development, fixed pricing with the public-private sector, treatment of recycled water at households at an affordable rate.

e. Water quality and Management Challenges

Every single drop of water requires minimum quality such as the presence of suspended and dissolved chemical and biological materials. The minimum quality of water must ensure no harm to living beings. The achievement of such criteria ensures diverse use of water with concerning objectives, measures, standards, and water purification. The water quality criteria should be flexible in nature as there is always a need for further modification over space and time while the authoritative value will not fit the enforcement requirement. Regarding this, the authority should focus on the safe use of

water sources at the same time protecting the fragile ecology of the city. The standard must be based on rationality, indigenous and scientific knowledge.

Water resource management and planning are some of the neglected areas in the city where sewage overflow has become a common phenomenon. Multiple times sewage pipes penetrate into drinking water supply pipelines resulting in havoc situation in the city. The problem of drinking water is becoming scary as it affects human beings in all forms due to a mismatch between the demand and supply sides. There is a need for demand regulation in the planning and management of water resources to meet the ever-increasing population demand that can be in terms of food. Water harvesting, following affordable pricing policy and adopting state of the art technology in collaboration with renowned institutions like IIT, IIMS DRDO, and ISRO. Water pricing is essential as it helps both in resource generation and efficient and effective utilization of water and discourages unnecessary waste of precious water.

Way Forward

a. Traditional Method of Drinking Water

The deterioration of water quality is not only a problem in Delhi but also dominant in most metropolitan cities across India. Delhi is blessed with sufficient water sources, which is substantial for consumption, allied activities in industry and agriculture, but their qualitative aspects getting deteriorated very rapidly due to anthropogenic activities. There are several methods of treating water scientifically together with traditional means.

a.1. filtration

Infiltration, muslin cloth is folded two or four times to remove suspended particles of a certain size. In this method, micro-organisms, harmful minerals like mercury, arsenic, and oil substances are not removed.

a.2. Beds

In this method, six to eight earthen pots are kept one over the other wherein all the pots have specific size holes except the bottom-most pot. Further, except for the bottom-most pot, all pots are filled one over other filled with

different materials such as beds through which water is allowed to pass easily. In the sequence, the top most pot has gravel bed, next below filled with a sand bed of thicker mesh, afterward coal, then next pot filled with charcoal and so on. Various beds absorb various oil matters, but the removal of micro-organisms and dissolved salt is not possible.

a.3 Boiling and Use of Alum

Boiling kills most micro-organisms while excess dissolved salts in the water get settled down. The boiled water has less nutritional value however it gives a lot of relief at times of urgent need. Adding alum in water will cause suspended particles to settle down due to the unique properties of alum-like coagulation. It has the capacity to kill micro-organisms, but it also changes the actual taste of water

b. Modern Water Purification Method

Purification of water is given great importance as most existing water bodies are getting contaminated due to malpractices.

b.1. Storage

Water is drawn out of different natural and artificial sources. Storage keeps water reserve from which further pollution is avoided. Around 90% of suspended impurities settled down within 24 hours by mere storage under the influence of gravity and water becomes crystal clear. The aerobic condition oxidizes organic matter present in water with the help of dissolved oxygen (O₂). The optimum period of river water storage is around 11 to 15 days during which pathogenic gradually die and collected water is safe.

b.2. Filtration and Disinfection

Filtration removes around 99% bacteria from water, besides other impurities. Any chemical which is aids disinfectant has to satisfy certain criteria such as it must be capable of destroying pathogens within the available contact line. The agent is not influenced by a series of chemical and physical properties like mineral constituents, pH, and temperature. It should not leave

any reaction able products that lead to making water toxic in any case. Available at a reasonable cost, safe, convenient, accessible, and affordable

c. Chlorination

Chlorination kills harmful bacteria but brings some change in water taste and odor. It controls algae growth, slime organisms, and assists coagulation. When chlorine is added to water hydrochloric acid (HCL) and hypochlorous acid (HCLO) are formed while HCL neutralized water's alkalinity. Chlorine act as the best disinfectant when the pH of water is around seven. When pH exceeds 8, then it is not a good option as 90% HCL gets ionized to HCLO. There are certain rules to be kept in mind to ensure chlorination such as water should be clear. The minimum recommended chlorine-free is 0.5 mg per hour.

d. Purification of Water on Small Scale

The most important cheapest method of good disinfection is mixing bleaching power in the well's water. It is necessary to ensure a regulated dose of chlorine into well water during emergencies. In the pot method of chlorination, two cylinders are needed one placed inside the other. Afterward, the pot is immersed about 1 meter below water level to avoid any damage by buckets used to draw water from the concerning spot. The device easily works for at least 2-3 weeks in small wells and contains around 4,500 liters of water withdrawal rate varies from 300 to 400 liters of water per day. In cities like Delhi where groundwater is playing a vital role in water supply must be treated properly with some simple, economic, and affordable method and de-fluoridation is a better option (Fig. 5). In de-fluoridation, aluminium salt and aluminium sulphate (alum) is applied to remove fluoride. It is applicable in both domestic and community water supply.

Fig. 5 Groundwater Consumption in Delhi (Adopted from Water Policy for Delhi, 2014 and Prepared by Author)

Suggestive Measures

1. Short-term Measures

1.a. Pollution Control at Urban Settlement Sources

It is very important to identify several sources of water pollution and there is a need to arrange them in the order of their severity, further plan a comprehensive control strategy accordingly. Delhi is a homeland for several sources of pollution and urban sewage planning would play a crucial role in water pollution mitigation. It should take of agriculture, industry, and domestic wastes. Several cities are located within the surroundings of Delhi and supplies products to the cities. The process of urbanization is one of the major causes of urban sprawl in population. Making sustainable cities and communities is the need of the hour.

1.b. Protection of Drinking Water Source

Yamuna and Ganga River are acting as major sources of water in Delhi, but these rivers are receiving untreated sewage from industries situated on their banks. Thereby, contaminated water sources can't be recovered and converted into potable drinking water even with the highest level of treatment with state of art technology. There were many incidences where Delhi's own untreated sewage is contaminating its drinking water source to a large

extent. Hence, such mismanagement should be stopped with immediate effect to contain drinking water pollution. The highest level of quality check is required to maintain the best possible available water quality with the limited resource in the city

2. Long-term Measure

The principal concern in the field of water management is the qualitative management of water resources with long-term measures. It emphasized four aspects domestic, industrial, hydropower production, and irrigation. The water quality deteriorates due to continuous and repeated use without considering the qualitative dimension of water. This condition warrants an immediate and rational evolution of better water quality assessment and management through strict implementation of pollution control measures within the city. The long-term aim of the pollution control program should focus on regions centered in the city. The program should be planned based on the region that is facing acute water shortage and degradation in existing water quality. The classification and zoning of problematic areas to ascertain potential pollution factors in each region should be taken into consideration. The long-term measure will brief the extent of attention needed in the identified region.

Conclusion

Water is the most precious resource on the earth because all living organisms utilize it for their growth and developmental activities and is the base of life forms on mother earth. Water can survive without human intervention, but human beings cannot survive without water. It covers around 71% of the earth's surface and only 0.3% are freshwater and potable which is found in rivers, lakes, ponds, soil moisture, and the atmosphere. Millions of people only in Delhi drink contaminated water despite knowing the fact that they will fall sick after drinking pollutant mixed water. Thousands of people die in the city due to water-borne diseases causing a huge burden on the exchequer of the city. A drop of water is much more than a sack of gold for a thirsty human being. There is a need for more awareness regarding water usage

among all sections of society. It is high time for mass public participation to solve essential, but the core issue of water contamination, supply, and demand before the circumstance becomes worse.

References

- Banerjee, B. (1999), *Use and Misuse of Water*, Geographical Review of India, Vol.60 (3).
- Banerjee, B. (1997), *Population Expansion, food Security and Sustainable Development*, Geographical Review of India, Vol.59 (1), pp 1-10.
- Bhattacharya, S. K. (1988) 'Problems of Water Supply in Congested City Areas-Calcutta, A case Study', in J. Pickford (Ed.) *Developing World Water*, Hong Kong: Grosvenor Press International.
- Bisht, S, Patra, B. A, Gupta, N. C, Arora, S, and Singh, R. A. (2007) Assessment of Drinking Water Quality of Delhi, India, University School of Environmental Management, G. G. S. I. P. University, New Delhi, India. *12th ISMAS-WS-2007, March 25-30, 2007, Cidade de Goa, Dona Paula, Goa Proceedings of 12th ISMAS Symposium cum RSP-1 Workshop on Mass Spectrometry*.
- Biswas, A. K. (1990), *Environmentally Sound Water Management*, oxford University Press, Delhi.
- Bourne, P. G. et al. (1984), *Water and Sanitation, Economic and Sociological Perspectives*, Academic Press Inc. London, pp. 2-19,70-91.
- Centre for Science and Environment, (2001), *A water Harvesting Manual for Urban Areas: Case Studies from Delhi*, Age of Enlightenment Publications, Faridabad.
- District Census Handbook, (2011), Village and Town-wise Primary Census Abstract, Directorate of Census Operations, Delhi.
- Government of India (1996) *Annual Plan 1996-97*, Planning Commission, New Delhi.
- Government of National Capital Territory of Delhi. (1995) *Delhi Statistical Hand Book*, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Government of the National Capital Territory of Delhi.
- Jairaj, B. (1995) *Regulating Ground Water of Delhi: Scope for legal Intervention Spatio-Economic Development Record*, Vol.2, (6), pp.42-46, New Delhi.
- Kittu, N. et al. (1996), *Ground Water Situation and Development Prospects in National Capital Region*, 22-23 November, Seminar Organised by INTACH, Water Resource of National Capital Region: Problems and Alternatives.
- Kundu, A. (1993) *In the Name of Urban Poor: Access to Basic Amenities*, Sage Publication, New Delhi.
- Kundu, A. (1991) *Micro-Environment in Urban Planning Access of Poor to Water Supply and Sanitation*, Economic and Political Weekly, Vol: 26 (37).
- Lackington, D. (1988) 'Solving Distribution Problems', in J. Pickford (Ed) *Developing World Water*, Hong Kong: Grosvenor Press International.
- National Institute of Urban Affairs (1986) *Management of Urban Services*, Research Study, Series Number 14, National Institute of Urban Affairs, New Delhi.
- National Institute of Urban Affairs (1988) *Upgrading Municipal Services: Norms and Financial Implications*, National Institute of Urban Affairs, New Delhi.
- National Institute of Urban Affairs (1991) *Basic Service and the Urban Poor*, Research Study Series Number 46, National Institute of Urban Affairs, New Delhi.
- Planning Commission (1985) *Seventh Five Year Plan 1985-90*, Vol. II, Government of India, New Delhi.

Journal of Water and Land Use Management
Volume 17, Issue 2

- Postel, S. (1985), *Conserving Water: The Untapped Alternative*, World Water paper-67, September.
- Reddy, R. (1998), *Urban Water Crisis: A Case Study of Jaipur*, Rawat Publication, Jaipur.
- Swamy, S. A. (1987) *Delhi Water Supply Schemes- Issues, Problems and Solutions*, A paper prepared for training workshop on "Urban Civic Services and Management" organized by TCPO, New Delhi.